

COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE MODEL FOR TOURISM SECTOR DEVELOPMENT IN THE SOUTH BANTEN REGION, BANTEN PROVINCE

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Abstract

The main problem in this research is that various stakeholders have not been integrated with infrastructure weaknesses in the Development of the Tourism Sector in the South Banten Region of Banten Province in the Collaborative Governance model. This study uses a qualitative method with a case study design. The study results reveal that the application of the collaborative governance model in realizing the development of the tourism sector in the South Banten Region of Banten Province is organized by the Regional Government (Department of Tourism and Culture) of Banten Province, which integrates the government, business and community activities. The collaboration model aims to ease the burden on public institutions (government), break the concentration of authority of public institutions that are too dominant and increase the participation of other stakeholders to proportionally share the roles of the parties in tourism management so that the channelling of the aspirations of the parties can be realized. This study found a robust leadership model to drive stakeholders and program transparency. Leadership and transparency are needed, especially for the Banten community with strong religious and traditional ties. Transparency is the key to the trust of all stakeholders, becoming a common problem and solving problems together. In other words, the development of this model is following current needs without compromising the right to meet the needs of future communities in the South Banten region, Banten Province.

Keywords: Model, Collaborative Governance, Tourism, Local Government.

A. INTRODUCTION

Tourism development is crucial as part of national development. The tourism industry has consistently achieved positive growth; tourist arrivals have proven to be able to encourage better economic, social and cultural benefits for the destinations they visit (Crouch & Ritchie, 1999; Tosun, 2000; Hall & Lew, 2009). Tourism economic growth is directly proportional to better people's incomes, and such conditions can be achieved if there is tourism development in the form of complete open transportation access, marketing and promotion of tourist destinations, and improvement of public infrastructure and tourism (Tosun, 2000; Enright & Newton). , 2004; Tao & Wall, 2009).

In order to realize the above tourism development, it is necessary to formulate a comprehensive and binding policy (Bramwell & Lane, 2000; Hall, 2008), as well as the involvement of all stakeholders in creating a directed and sustainable tourism ecosystem (Muhanna, 2006; Risteskia et al., 2012). As mandated by Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning tourism that "the preparation of government tourism development policies, strategies and programs must be guided by tourism planning that is integrated into a systematic, planned, integrated, sustainable, and responsible manner while still protecting religious values, the culture that lives in society, the preservation and quality of the environment, as well as the national interest.

Each region has its strategy for implementing sustainable tourism development with the National tourism program, especially in opening tourist destinations and absorbing the local workforce to improve community welfare (Susanto, 2016; Arida & Sunarta, 2017; Buditiawan, 2020). One of the common ways to maximize the potential of regional tourism is that local governments are always trying to expand tourism investment opportunities by issuing regional regulations as a first step to solving problems that occur (Latuconsina et al., 2013; Azhari, 2019).

The main goal of tourism development is to increase foreign exchange earnings for the country and to hope that tourism can act as an agent of development (Tosun, 2006; Hawkins & Mann, 2007). From an economic point of view, there are at least eight advantages of developing tourism in Indonesia: First, increasing business opportunities. Second, job opportunities. Third, increasing tax revenue. Fourth, increasing national income. Fifth, accelerate the process of equity. Sixth, increasing the added value of cultural products. Seventh, expanding the domestic product market. Furthermore, it has a multiplier effect on the economy as a result of spending on tourists, investors and foreign trade (Yeti, 2008; Rismiyanto & Danangdjojo, 2015).

The number of foreign and domestic tourists visiting Banten Province from 2018 to 2020 shows a significant difference between foreign and domestic tourists to the North Banten region, namely Kab. Tangerang, Kab. Serang, Tangerang City, Cilegon City Serang City and South Tanggelang City were 8858.61, i.e. 85.67%, compared to the South Banten Region namely Lebak Regency and Pandeglang Regency, as many as 1481.29, i.e. 14.33% (CBS, 2021), from From the data, it can be seen that the number of visitors to the South Banten region is less than the number of visitors to the North Banten region, especially foreign tourists, allegedly due to the imbalance in the development of tourism supporters in the South Banten Region compared to the North Banten Region (Sutjipto, 2014). The objective condition that becomes an obstacle to the development of South Banten tourism is the limited infrastructure; it interferes with the connectivity of tourist visits from Jakarta and the North Banten region, and overall, the potential for South Banten tourism objects has not been handled well managed (Darma, 2019).

The step to maximize tourism development to improve the quality and quantity of tourist destinations in Banten Province following the formulation of policies set by the local government requires collaborative governance between the government and the private sector to accelerate the achievement of tourism development targets that require resources and support from all parties. Collaborative governance is needed because of the many asynchronous and lack of coordination in handling a case from weak networking and cooperation between institutions (Darma, 2019).

The use of the collaborative governance model theory from Emerson & Nabatchi (2015) in tourism development research in the South Banten Region of Banten Province is based on the suitability of the interpretation of research problems with the operationalization of the dimensions contained in theory, which in reality are real problems of tourism in the southern region of Banten. As the basis of analysis to explore the collaboration process, namely: First, System Context, as an initial mapping of the consensus-oriented process, this process is not only limited to face-to-face dialogue. The six main elements of the system context include

resource or service conditions, policy and legal frameworks, socio-economic and cultural characteristics, network characteristics, political dynamics & power relations, and historical conflicts that affect trust levels. The external environment of this system context creates opportunities and constraints and influences the general parameters within which GCR opens and operates (Emmerson & Gerlak, 2014).

Second, Drivers provide energy to persuade the gathered collaboration participants. The presence of the driver recognized by the participant, the more likely the GCR will start. Drivers, namely: leadership, powerful incentives, interdependence, or uncertainty required to initiate GCR. The more drivers present and recognized by the participants, and the more likely a GCR will start (Kurniadi & Suryadi, 2021). Third, collaborative dynamics (Collaborative Dynamics), conceptually the stages in collaborative dynamics as a cycle or repetitive interaction; three components interact with each other in collaborative dynamics, namely: principled engagement, shared motivation, and joint action capacity (joint capacity) (Dewi, 2019).

Fourth, Output Collaborative Actions, collaborative actions are the core of the collaborative governance framework. Collaborative actions are the main result of a linear collaboration process that is sometimes associated with impact (Arrozaaq, 2016). The background of the collaborative action is the difficulty of achieving the goal if it is only carried out by one tourism group or organization in the South Banten area, Banten Province. Fifth, Collaborative Outcomes consist of impacts & adaptation. The purpose of Collaboration is to produce the desired outcome together because Collaboration involves collaborative activities to increase the capacity of self and others to achieve common goals (Islamy, 2018).

Collaborative governance is a crucial stage that determines the effectiveness of a development implementation by the government and has become one of the instruments that significantly determines the quality, effectiveness and optimization of achieving the goals of local government programs in improving people's welfare (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Lahat & Sher-Hadar, 2021).), including synchronization and integration in developing tourism comprehensively and synergistically in the South Banten Region, Banten Province.

Based on the arguments and empirical conditions above, the focus of this research is directed at the collaborative governance model in realizing the development of the tourism sector in the South Banten Region of Banten Province, which is organized by the Regional Government (Tourism and Culture Office) of Banten Province which integrates government, business and community activities. Thus there is a need for Collaboration between the parties involved in managing tourism in Banten Province. The collaboration model aims to ease the burden on public institutions, break the concentration of authority of public institutions that are too dominant and increase the participation of other stakeholders in order to proportionally share the roles of the parties in tourism management so that the channelling of the aspirations of the parties can be realized.

B. METHOD

The research method used by the researcher is a qualitative research method with a case study approach, namely research events, basic things (real-life events), which are ongoing, not something that has passed, meaning that the data collected is not a collection of numbers, but rather from in-depth interviews, observation activities, field notes, official documents and others (Herdiansyah, 2015). In this study, the researcher uses the Case Study method by focusing on one particular object that is appointed as a case to be studied in depth to be able to uncover the reality behind the phenomenon, as a process of studying or understanding a case and at the same time looking for the results. Based on the thoughts above, the researcher tries to explore what information can be learned or drawn from the case of implementing the development of the tourism sector in the South Banten Region, Banten Province, by making direct observations and being directly involved. One of the essential things to consider in selecting cases, researchers believe that further and in-depth scientific knowledge can be obtained (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

The process of processing and analyzing qualitative data is carried out in stages, including data reduction, where the data obtained is written in the form of a detailed description, then reduced, summarized, selected the main ones, focused on the essential things, found themes or patterns, and arranged more systematically. Then the data presentation or display is arranged systematically based on the type and pattern, then arranged in charts or narratives to form a series of meaningful information according to the problem. As for drawing conclusions and verification, it means that after the reduction and presentation of the data is carried out, conclusions are drawn, or verification is carried out.

C. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Theory of Collaborative Governance Model of tourism development in the South Banten Region, Banten Province

The use of the collaborative governance model theory from Emerson & Nabatchi (2015) in tourism development research in the South Banten Region of Banten Province is based on the suitability of the interpretation of research problems with the operationalization of the dimensions contained in theory, which in reality are real problems of tourism in the southern region of Banten. As the basis of analysis to explore the collaboration process, namely:

System context factor

The Banten Province Tourism Development Master Plan (RIPP) as a policy and legal framework is integral to the National Tourism Development Master Plan. RIPP is intended as a direction for developing tourism development in the Banten area by prioritizing the prosperity and welfare of the community based on the preservation of the natural and cultural environment, increasing love for the homeland, developing the people's economy, increasing tourism development performance and increasing Regional Original Income (PAD).

In order to remain sustainable, tourism development must pay attention to aspects of order, security, cleanliness, beauty and public safety following applicable regulations (Utama, 2015). Tourism development is based on an integrated mechanism for cross-sectoral development programs, which include Central, Provincial, Regency/City agencies, the community and the private sector. In addition, to further develop tourism, the Banten Provincial government also involves other stakeholders, namely the local community and entrepreneurs. One of the things that the Banten Provincial government has done is to involve and develop the MSME sector. This is done to channel the spirit of development to the people of Banten Province, especially in the southern region of Banten.

Factor Drivers

The importance of Drivers is to encourage collaborative governance participants who are gathered by reducing the initial costs of implementing collective action and then managing collaborative dynamics. Some experts describe collaborative processes as a linear series of steps or cognitive stages that occur over time, from problem definition to setting instructions and implementation (Millan, 2019). This is where the importance of building trust is in transferring information in the tourism sector. Counselling with the main actors between stakeholders requires a condition that promotes mutual trust so that the communication process can run effectively and innovation as the message to be conveyed can be accepted.

Several things are needed so that the community, the private sector/business as the communication target, can trust the government to achieve the tourism development program. This is where the importance of building trust is in transferring information in the tourism sector. Counselling with the main actors between stakeholders requires a condition that promotes mutual trust so that the communication process can run effectively and innovation as the message to be conveyed can be accepted. Several things are needed so that the community, the private sector/entrepreneurs as communication targets can put their trust in the government to achieve the tourism development program.

Collaborative Dynamic Factors

The development of tourist destinations in an area requires the contribution and cooperation of tourism stakeholders. Stakeholders as stakeholders in tourism success here are interpreted as individuals, groups or organizations that have an interest in, are involved in, or are influenced (positively or negatively) by tourism development activities or programs. Each stakeholder has a different role that needs to be understood so that the development of tourism objects and attractions in an area can be realized and appropriately implemented (Aas et al., 2005).

Commitment to the process must be maintained so that motivation continues to grow. Cross-sectoral cooperation between stakeholders in collaboration forums requires mutual understanding, reducing sectoral egos to achieve synergies between sectors. Preparation of plans in collaboration forums must have an impact on mutual benefits in the context of solving problems faced, related to collaboration results are a shared responsibility between actors (Innes & Booher, 2003).

The hope to be achieved is good tourism development according to the development master plan. The fundamental key is the attitude of mutual understanding embedded in each stakeholder's soul. Alternatively, this mutual understanding may be the initial step towards the final rung of the long collaborative collaboration process between the government, the private sector, and the community. All three are considered stakeholders in the success of Banten regional tourism development.

Collaborative Actions Output Factor

Determining the tourism development program simultaneously means setting targets to be achieved. The achievement of tourism development targets is evaluated periodically. Tourism activities for the association become a blessing of luck. With advanced tourism activities, the region and its cultural customs are also lifted, brought to be known by visitors/tourists. This is an advantage for indigenous peoples, so it must be supported for more advanced tourism concerned with local communities' potential. Is the benefit only for indigenous peoples, apparently not because the association feels this? Investments invested in this sector can produce profitable results. The association is not useless as a front line in tourism promotion and branding efforts. This signifies that travellers' trust in the association is growing. The government will also see our serious performance working in this tourism sector. The local government provides the ease of taking care of permits for entrepreneurs engaged in tourism development. Optimism can produce acceleration so that the potential of existing tourist destinations in the area can bring in tourists.

Collaborative Outcomes Factor

Commitment to building a win-win tourism solution between the government, the private sector, and the community must be built in partnership. The basis for conducting partnerships is the principle of a win-win solution where each partnering party must benefit together. The marketing aspect of tourist destinations has been carried out so far, namely to attract tourists who visit tourist destinations at several levels, both local, regional and international, to make more tourists come, stay longer and spend more money. Attract as many tourists as possible who come to use all the services provided. We also do many promotions. Marketing activities seek to disseminate information, influence/persuade, and/or remind the target market of their products to be willing to visit the attractions offered. To increase business enthusiasm, especially for investors developing special economic zones for tourism, the tourism office provides incentives for ease of licensing, access to road infrastructure, electricity, and others. On the other hand, we also always carry out periodic evaluations to see the progress of achieving tourism development targets.

2. Barriers to the Development of the Tourism Sector in the South Banten Region, Banten Province

Lebak Regency and Pandeglang Regency, Banten Province, commonly referred to as the South Banten and North Banten regions, are Tangerang Regency, Serang Regency, Tangerang City, Cilegon City, Serang City, South Tangerang City. The two regions between North and South experience development gaps due to differences in resources, financial structure and

availability of infrastructure. The economic development of a region aims to improve people's welfare and economic growth. The availability of infrastructure is one of the drivers of economic growth to accelerate the development process, especially if we want to increase the flow of tourists to tourism development.

Physical and social infrastructure can be defined as the basic physical needs of organizing the structural system needed for economic security in the public sector and the private sector as services and facilities needed for the economy to function correctly (Ompusunggu, 2018). The physical infrastructure that supports structural networks such as facilities includes roads, bridges, trains, clean water, airports, irrigation networks, canals, reservoirs, embankments, waste management, electricity networks, telecommunications, and ports. Social infrastructure for basic needs includes schools and hospitals (Surya, 2016).

Banten Governor Wahidin Halim is strongly committed to improving the quality of road infrastructure to prosper the community and regional boost progress, especially in the southern region, which is known as an underdeveloped area. The ongoing development and improvement program for road infrastructure can now relieve Banten Province, especially Pandeglang and Lebak Regencies, from the status of underdeveloped areas. Of course, what happened in Lebak and Pandeglang regencies included improving the quality of road infrastructure to facilitate the community's economic activities and supported by better public transportation facilities as well as expanding community economic access. Most importantly, the fulfilment of other essential services, such as education and health, continues to be improved through a synergy program between the district government and the provincial government.

In addition to infrastructure, the obstacle to tourism development in South Banten is Human Resources, according to one informant who stated that the problem in the aspect of human resources is the number and quality of workers in the tourism sector, both at the manager and implementation level, are still very limited. Some workers who directly deal with consumers (tourists) still need to be equipped with service knowledge and tour guides, where mastery of foreign languages and tourism knowledge needs to be improved. The role of institutions such as higher education, tourism associations, and local government agencies/agencies has not been maximized in preparing skilled workers in the tourism sector.

Another obstacle factor is the lack of discipline from visitors. Examples of cases around the natural attractions of Mount Halimun, Mount Kencana, Tanjung Lesung beach and others. The condition of existing tourist objects is indicated to be poorly maintained due to a lack of discipline from visitors. Hence, the tourist attraction area looks like it lacks cleanliness. Visitors should be equally responsible for preserving the natural environment in Lebak and Pandeglang Regencies tourist attractions. The behaviour of tourists, especially local tourists, needs to be educated and campaigned continuously so that they want to participate in maintaining and caring for them. So that the tourist attraction area still looks clean and looks well-maintained. This is part of the convenience that must be served at every tourist attraction.

3. Collaborative Governance Model for Tourism Sector Development in the South Banten Region, Banten Province

In order to realize tourism development and overcome obstacles in the implementation process, the implementation of integrated tourism development in accordance with the assumption of Perda no. 6 of 2019, requires a collaborative management model that combines elements of the user community (community, private sector/business/entrepreneurs) and the government. This management model implies that development is not only the responsibility of the government but also of all stakeholders. The secret of getting ahead is getting started; getting started is the most difficult challenge for collaborative governance. As with all matters of collective action, it is difficult to stimulate individuals to act beyond their self-interest and cooperate on common issues. It is difficult to stimulate heterogeneous groups of people to work collaboratively across organizations and sectors.

It is difficult for the government to work alone in carrying out development due to limited sources of funds, infrastructure and human resources. This collaboration model aims to optimize all resources and increase the participation of other stakeholders. There is no domination of certain parties over others in implementing tourism development. Through this model, the implementation of tourism development is carried out by uniting related institutions, especially the community and government as well as other stakeholders in every resource management process, starting from planning, implementation, utilization and supervision.

Research on Collaborative Governance in the Development of the Tourism Sector in the South Banten Region of Banten Province uses the analytical basis or collaborative governance theory proposed by Emerson & Nabatchi (2015). The authors use their thoughts to understand the framework of integrative, collaborative governance and make their theoretical ideas the leading framework in this writing. The research novelty found in the model below:

Figure 1: Model of Collaborative Governance for Tourism Development in South Banten Banten Province

The development program for developing tourism destinations in the South Banten region needs to pay attention to local wisdom. All of these tourism potentials cannot be claimed as private property, but this is community property (cultural heritage) but a noble cultural heritage. Local governments cannot impose their will or only follow the wishes of investors and entrepreneurs in the tourism sector. So, it is worth taking into account and considering the culture and customs of the local community. In general, the people of South Banten live in a robust kinship system and a deep-rooted patronage culture. Ulama and Jawara are community leaders who commonly become role models for Banten society and culture.

Regarding the driver's aspect, leadership is essential in establishing partnership relationships with private representatives/investors to discuss tourism infrastructure issues in a Tripartite Cooperation Institution (LKS) forum. Ideally, the forum should be initiated by the local government in order to build trust.

Collaborative dynamics consists of three interactive components: principle engagement, shared motivation, and joint action capacity. The three components of collaborative dynamics work together interactively, or steps are taken sequentially to implement a common goal of Collaborative Governance. Collaborative Governance actions can lead to results both inside and outside the regime; thus, in the figure, arrows extend from the action box to indicate impacts (i.e., results in the field) and potential adaptations (changes in complex situations or issues) both in the context of the system and within Collaborative Governance itself.

Leadership in tourism development in South Banten occupies a very strategic position. Leadership does not have to be good at everything, does not have to appear in every development activity, and does not have to supervise all the activities of the apparatus. However, he firmly believes that the entire tourism development process can be completed according to his plan. It is from the commitment of the government and stakeholders that all the potentials and initiatives of the people, along with public participation, will come forward and be mobilized consistently to produce regional progress.

The tourism industry has consistently been able to achieve positive growth, tourist arrivals have proven to be able to encourage better economic, social and cultural benefits for the destinations they visit. In order to realize this tourism development, it is necessary to formulate a comprehensive and binding policy and involve all stakeholders in creating a sustainable and targeted tourism ecosystem (Sasmito et al., 2020).

Furthermore, tourism development in the South Banten Region will impact the people's welfare in Pandeglang and Lebak Regencies. Tourism has become a locomotive that drives the community's economy because of its unique nature, namely tourism potential based on natural beauty, history and culture (Kapioru, 2019). Thus, to further spur the integration of tourism development so that it becomes more qualified, effective and optimal in achieving its goals, it is encouraged by different regulations on tourism development in Banten province for the southern region of Banten.

Inadequate infrastructure and facilities, especially regarding tourist service facilities such as tourist transportation services, hotel and lodging facilities, interior arrangement and maintenance of tourist attractions. The limited interest of investors investing in the tourism sector, among others, is due to road infrastructure, electricity, and internet networks. They must be built by developers who will open tourist attractions (Zakiah, 2019). Although Banten Province has diverse tourism potential, marketing activities have not been directed and well planned. Product offerings that are often not in accordance with market tastes as well as promotional efforts that have not been planned and directed, the quality of promotional materials is still less attractive and promotions carried out by the government and the private sector are not coherent.

The step to maximize tourism development to improve the quality and quantity of tourist destinations in Banten Province following the formulation of policies set by the local government requires collaborative governance between the government and the private sector to accelerate the achievement of tourism development targets that require resources and support from all parties. Collaborative governance is needed because of the many asynchronous and lack of coordination in handling a case due to weak networking and cooperation between institutions.

Commitment and transparency between the government and stakeholders in the collaborative process of tourism development in the South Banten Region can create poor trust between sectors, which has an impact on the low commitment of investors planning the development of tourist areas and, on the other hand, public distrust of the government and the private sector is

marked by widespread action against the development of special economic zones for tourism. The community refuses to let go of their land, which is designated as a special economic zone for tourism and includes a tourism destination development program in several Banten Province areas with superior tourist attractions. Furthermore, the success of Collaboration is determined by how much the actors are committed to the process (commitment to process); the local government's efforts to improve the quality of tourist destinations through the Tourism Destination Development Program aims to increase tourist visits to Banten province to boost the local economy. The implementation of regional development in the tourism sector has not yet been implemented in a synergistic collaborative manner.

The tourism destination development program by the Banten Provincial Government in the southern Banten region needs to pay attention to local wisdom. You cannot stick with the wishes of the local government or follow the desires of the owners of capital, entrepreneurs who want to invest in the tourism sector. So, the local government should take into account and consider the culture and customs of the local community. In general, the people of South Banten live in a robust kinship system and a deep-rooted patronage culture. Community leaders who are commonly used as pantans for the people and culture of Banten are Ulama and Jawara.

D. CONCLUSION

The development of the tourism sector in the South Banten Region of Banten Province is intended to increase the role and function of local government, mainly related to the function of developing tourism infrastructure that can benefit the community's economy by prioritizing the prosperity and welfare of the community based on the preservation of the natural and cultural environment, improving tourism development performance. Moreover, increasing Regional Original Income. The policy framework for the development of tourism destinations in Banten Province has been stipulated by Banten Province Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019 concerning the Banten Province Tourism Development Master Plan which is still general regarding all areas of Banten Province. Tourism development in the South Banten region is based on the advantages of local wisdom. Development of tourist attractions through attractions based on nature, art, history, social, culture and community religion. Tourism development motivates the development of community life and creativity and strengthens belief in the truth and virtue of community identity. The obstacles to accelerating tourism development in the South Banten region, Banten Province, are the availability of tourist destination facilities and infrastructure, commitment and transparency between the government and stakeholders in the tourism development process which often arises due to differences in characteristics and interests and the absence of regional regulations specifically for tourism development in the South Banten Region which is integrated and transparent by involving all stakeholders.

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